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The Wavefunction of the Angles

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ABSTRACT: We give our point of view in that the wavefunction ψ could be a wave of angles due to rotations in the fifth dimension

KEYWORDS: Quantum mechanics; hidden variables; vortex dynamics; spacetime; relativity

INTRODUCTION

After 35 years of research and a lot of calculations accessible through the reference section the author presents his view on the nature of the wavefunction. It involves all physics in describing a vorticity wave coming from change of angles from relativistic effects. A lot of thermodynamic quantities are involved and cyclic procedures are described.

MAIN PART

The wavefunction ψ represents a wave of angles since ψ is dimensionless and so are the angles. These angles exist in the five dimensional world and are perceived as solid angles in our four dimensional world of relativity. It is so because the magnetic field is the gradient of ϕ depending on the solid angles. This wave is also a pressure wave as the relativistic pressure induced by mass curvature is applied through solid angles and surfaces and pressure is created by vorticity. We are also aware that vorticity is of greater value in the areas sharp angles. The angle of rotation is related to the phase of the wavefunction. The wave is measuring the progression of time. This is why the standing wave of the electron in the atom accounts for frozen time.

Now, the solid angles are the way of observation of an event and that way the particle may be assumed to be in many places. The phenomenon is associated with pulsating magnetic monopoles which create this wave because their potential is such. Magnetic monopoles therefore are not said to exist at least as particles only as pulsating dipoles which create the spin of the particle. The phase is connected to the action at least in the semiclassical approximation so these angle waves carry action wave fronts. Dirac used the angle bracket notation to point out this fact. There is the action angle formulation describing these relationships

Circular movement is an accelerating one and according to the relativity the length of the circle and therefore the angles are changing. This is similar to our situation except all this is caused by mass and the spin of the particle two properties closely connected.

CONCLUSIONS

We have finally attributed an angle wave to the wavefunction. We believe that this is a spacetime warp like vibration arising from rotations in the fifth dimension

Soon we expect a book to be published giving more clear evidence regarding the matter.

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